

A Study of Sambuddhe gĕthĕ

Win Win Yi*

Abstract

Sambuddhe¹ gĕthas are not taught by the Buddha or not from the Pĕĕi, Aĕĕhathĕ and ĕĕĕ recognized as Theravĕda texts. They were composed by Srĕĕa-kĕ and Myanmar monks well-versed Pĕĕi.² Sambuddhe gĕthĕ is a prayer dedicated to 512028 previous Enlightened Buddhas.

Introduction

The gĕthĕ is found in the introduction of the Tathĕgatuppatti³ by venerable one composed the book based on the sayings, "cintitaĕ sattasa-khyeyaĕ"⁴ as mentioned in the Sotattakĕ chronicle of the Buddhas. The statement of the Sotattakĕ is based on the Yasodharĕ Therĕ Apadĕna.

"Brahmadevaĕca sambuddhaĕ, gotamaĕ Lokanĕyakaĕ
Aĕĕesaĕ Lokanĕthĕnaĕ, Sa-gamaĕ te bahuĕ mayĕ."⁵

The above address was uttered by Yasodharĕ there "the association of you, the venerable one and I was many as I have been aspired from the Porĕĕa Gotama Buddha and Brahmadeva Buddha."

So, it is to note that this Sambuddhe gĕthĕ is a prayer dedicated to 512028 previous Enlightened Buddhas.

As there is the evidence in the literature, there also found the archaeological discoveries concerning the Sambuddhe distinctively. On these grounds, it is today that the Sambuddhe gĕthĕ was reliable in the time of king Anawratha in Myanmar in 406 ME, 1044 AD. It is known by the report of the officer of inscriptions (Kyaukar Wun) in Myanmar in 1947-48.⁶

In that report, it mentioned that the monk, U Cintĕ from the Nga Ou village, entrance of Momate forest, Mokuk city made four ancient shrines situated on the river bank of shweli dig by his dream, thee found the Sambuddhe votive tablet together with relics. collar-bone,

* Dr., Professor (Head), Department of Oriental Studies, Bago University

¹ Sambuddhe = Saĕ + buddhe

Saĕ = by self

Buddhe = to the Buddhas known the four Noble Truth

= To the Buddhas known the Four Noble Truths by self

² By dhamĕcariya U Aye Naing: Piĕakakyangantawĕ aswanhtat gĕthĕ parittaw mya.

³ Tu = From reverse side of folio 'ka' to obverse side of folio 'kĕ'

⁴ Sott, p. *

⁵ Ap-a-II-268.

⁶ By Myint Swe: Myanmarnainggan and Sambuddhe article Myatna-galĕ cĕcaun, Vol II, No. 1, July.

images, shrines and votive tablets of the Buddha. On the back of a votive tablet, these found three PĒĀi lines:

“Eso bhagavĒ mahĒrĒja sĒri aniruddhadevena kato,
VimuttatthaÑ sahatthenavĒti ”.

This Buddha image was made by the king with the title of “Anawratha” by his hand for the essence of freedom.

The inscription officer remarked that these three PĒĀi lines were the hand-writing of king AnawrathĒ. Therefore, by these three lines from the votive tablets, the votive tablets of life of the Buddha and Sambuddhe discovered from the bank of Shweli are obvious belonging to so Pagan period. So it is to note that this Sambuddhe gĒthĒ has been existed in Myanmar since Pagan period as a historical foot-print.

Two kinds of Sambuddhe gĒthĒs

There are two kinds of Sambuddhe SrĒla-kĒ and Myanmar. SrĒla-kĒ Sambuddhe gĒthĒ has the origin in SrĒla-kĒ and Myanmar Sambuddhe has the origin in Myanmar respectively.

As it is called “Sambuddhe” in the SrĒla-kĒ Sambuddhe does not contain the word “Sambuddhe”. However it is a prayer dedicated to the previous Enlightened Buddhas in the number of 512028. It has the same beginning “Sambuddhe aĀhavĒsaĀca”, cause objective and meaning are like the Myanmar Sambuddhe gĒthĒ. So it seems SrĒla-kĒ Sambuddhe was used by the successive teachers.

SrĒla-kĒ Sambuddhe ¹

BuddhĒ annunnĒmariyĒ susa-khaye, BuddhĒ annunnĒsuhalĒ dhisa-khaye,
BuddhĒ riyĒ he Saku lakkhakappake, VandĒmi tejeĀhanaruttame same.

The meaning there are 12500 Enlightened Buddha during the seven asa-khyeyas, 387000 Enlightened Buddhas during the nine asa-khyeyyas, 12 Enlightened Buddhas during the four asa-khyeyyas and 16 Enlightened Buddha during a hundred thousand asa-khyeyyas. I worship those 512028 Buddhas who had entered the ParinibbĒna.

That gĒthĒ describes the duration of the time that the Future Buddha aspired to be a Buddha mentally is seven asa-khyeyas where 125000 Buddhas such as Brahmadeva become Enlightened. There 387000 Buddhas such as porĒĀgotama were Enlightened during the nine asa-khyeyas where the Future Buddha aspired to be a Buddha verbally. There 11 Buddhas became Enlightened during the four asa-khyeyyas where the Future Buddha aspired to be a Buddha both mentally and verbally. During a hundred thousand worlds where 16 Buddhas became Enlightened separately.

¹ By chĒbhannĒ sayardaw : “KavimaĀĒanamedanĒkyan”

They are totally 512028 in number. In this way the significant description of the Sumbuddhe gĒtha is to be noted.

Myanmar Sambuddhe gĒthĒ

It depicts in the TathĒgattuppatti thus;

1. Sambuddhe aĀhavĒsaĀca. dvĒdasaĀca sahasake,
paĀcasata sahasĒni, namĒmi sirasĒ mahaĀ
2. TesaĀ dhammaĀca saĀghaĀca, Ēdarena namĒmahaĀ.
3. NamakkĒrĒ nubhĒvena, hitvĒ sabbe uppaddave,
anekĒ antarĒyĒpi, vinassantu asesato.

Meaning of the Sambuddhe gĒthĒ

I worship the 28 and 510000 Buddhas with my head : I worship the Dhamma of those Buddhas and SaĀgha respectively. Because of the result of the good deeds through worship, may all danger dispel without reservation.

In this Myanmar Sambuddhe gĒthĒ, it is mentioned the total 51200 Buddha Enlightened during the seven asa-khyeyyas and nine asa-khyeyyas under whom the Future Buddha aspired to be a Buddha mentally and verbally. Then it describes the 28 Enlightened Buddhas during four asa-khyeyyas and a hundred thousand worlds under whom the Future Buddha aspired to be a Buddha both mentally verbally. So there are totally Buddhas in the number of 512028.

This is the difference between the SrĒla-kĒ and Myanmar Sambuddhe gĒthĒs.

In spite of description is different, the indication and the cause are the same. However the SrĒla-kĒ Sambuddhe is the prayer for the Buddha and Myanmar Sambuddhe is the prayer for the Buddha, Dhamma and SaĀgha. Besides it endowed with more energy as it contains the wish of the worshiper.

Sambuddhe gĒthĒ with addition

The Myanmar Sambuddhe gĒthĒ as mentioned in the TathĒgattuppatti has two and half stanzas. Now to the No. 2 stanza, the two lines "appakaĀ vĒlukaĀ ga-gaĀ anantaĀ nibbutaĀ jinaĀ" are added. When the addition took place and who fulfilled it were unknown. It is difficult to say it exactly. It can give the reason of the addition.

In the history Sambuddhe Inscription, a verse from the Buddha ApadĒna is mentioned.

"AhaĀpi pubbabuddhesu, BuddhattamabhipatthayiĀ.

manasĒyeva hutvĒna. dhammarĒjĒ asa-khayĒ "

"I aspired to be a Buddha from the previous Buddha mentally. They are uncountable. They are infinite".

With the reason, it is composed "appakē vĕĕkē ga~gē, anantē nibbutē jinē (1a) asesato". Therefore it is to note that the addition is depended on the Buddha Apadēna.

Thai Sambuddhe

In addition, a kind of Sambuddhe, protective gēthē decorated with the attributes of the Buddha is found in the "Sabbama~galēdhammadesanē " composed by the patron sayadaw, the venerable Vĕsavĕbhivañsa of the Visuddhĕrĕma monastery, Yangon. The author of the book said that he got it from a Thai monk.

Safety Sambuddhe gēthē in Pĕli decoration

(Sambuddhe aĕhavĕsaĕca) Buddho me nĕtho,

sattapĕkĕrañ Buddhañ saraĕañ gacchĕmi.

i, svĕ, su. Buddhañ saraĕañ gato,

sabbabhayĕ vinassantu.

(dvĕdasaĕca sahasake) dhammo me nĕtho,

sattapĕkĕrañ, dhammañ saraĕañ gacchĕmi,

i, svĕ, su, dhammañ saraĕañ gato,

sabbarogĕ vinassantu.

(Paĕcasata sahasĕni) sañgho me nĕtho,

sattapĕkĕrañ, sañghañsaraĕañ gacchĕmi.

i, svĕ, su, sañghañsaraĕañ gato,

sabbadukkhĕ vinassantu.

(Tesañ dhammaĕca sañghaĕca ĕdarena namĕmahañ

namakkĕrĕnubhĕvena) a, u, ma.

(hitvĕsabbe upaddavĕ) ma, u, a.

Aneka antarĕyĕpi vinassantu asesato,

saĕĕabuddhĕ paĕimĕbuddho arahañ bhagavĕti.

In fact, as the sambuddhe gēthēs are based on the commentaries of the Yasodharĕ Apadēna and Buddha Apadaĕna. Therefore they seem to be believable and acceptable.

The Sambuddhe rubric square (In) under the wall of Mandalay city

It was used when the king Mindone constructed the royal city in 1211 ME, 1859 AD. That is known by the report of Sir Richard Temple in the Indian Antiquary magazine. According to that report, it is mentioned thus:

In 1889, Sir Richard who served as military officer in Mandalay broke the brick pole of the royal city wall. He found there the stone box with the depth of four and half feet. These found silver magic square of 8 inches. The inscription in the box reads that the king, Mindone founded being erected ornamented pole in Mandalay on the 6th year of his reign in 2401 BE, 1219 ME. He caused the stone box to be buried at three yards distance on the left direction of the city wall where the red door was.

On the grounds of this condition, the Sambuddhe gĕthĕ is not only for recitation but also as a buried rubric square for safety net.

			sa	ke	ma	ppa			
	sĕ	ssa	sĕ	a	mbu	pa	haÑ	sa	
	ĕ	to	mi	mĕ	u	ne	dda	Òca	
re	mĕ	ra	ha	sa	ve	ddhe	bbe	te	tvĕ
Òca	sa	da	na	mi	ma	se	ka	a	sa
na	na	sa	da	a	a	vi	haÑ	hi	saÑ
Òca	gha	bhĕ	yĕ	ma	ssa	na	nta	ta	òòha
	ni	dvĕ	ntu	ve	rĕ	na	na	dha	
	nu	saÑ	ssĕ	Òca	kĕ	mma	sa	vĕ	
			rĕ	Òca	ha	sa			

(2401 BE, 1219 ME)

King Mindone founded being erected ornamented pole in Mandalay on the 6th year of his reign.

Monhin Sambuddhe Shrine

The Monhin Sambuddhe pagoda was constructed seven miles distance, south east of Monywa city, Sakaing district, Upper Myanmar at 6:30 to 7'0 clock of Friday morning, on 5th waxing day of the second verso. The forty monk headed by the Monhintoya Sayadaw recited partitas and founded the base having the police men and trustees of the Pagodas stoked the pole and fined the four missiles. From the day beginning with the staking upto the completion, it took twelve years. It was totally finished on the 3rd waxing of Tabaung in 1313 ME.¹

¹ By Susuka : Sambuddheamyomyo and Tankho Siddhimyah, 123-124

In the construction of the great pagoda, without taking help from any engineer, the Sayadawgyi instructed the supervisor of the monastery, Sayadawgyi U NĒrada and the mason, Saya Han gyi according to his vision. As the Pagoda was constructed according to his instruction, it became a wonderful Sambuddhe Pagoda in these days.¹

The venerable Monhin Sayadawgyi constructed the Sambuddhe Pagoda with these intentions: it is more beneficial to pay devotional services to the Buddhas under whom Gotama Buddha aspired to be a Buddha than to worship the only Buddha; it develops the faith and the benefit of mundane and supramundane deeds which lead to free from dangerous catastrophic.²

One can be endowed with various benefits reciting the Sambuddhe gĒthĒ without knowing the meaning. It is more beneficial for those who know the meaning.

Those who worship the Buddha images and those who make the Buddha images are more beneficial. Thus he said by the successive teachers.

In side and outside of the Sambuddhe Pagoda, the images small and great of the Pagoda are mentioned in the number of 582363 according to the La-kĒ-mya, Shwe, Ngwe, Sein, thĒ, saung, Sambuddhe rou pwa paung. According to the Sambuddhe gĒthĒ, there are 512028 Buddhas. However, it is mentioned 582363 in the La-kĒ, history of the account, 70335 are extras. The extras are according to the second stanza of the Sambuddhe gĒthĒ, "appakĒ vĒlukĒ ga-gĒ, anantĒ jinĒ " the Enlightened Buddhas are numerous like the sand of vĒlukĒ and Ga-gĒ. They are uncountable. Indicated that statement, extra Buddha images are inserted.

The construction of the Sambuddhe shrine and paying homage to it indicate not only the supramundaneness but also present life. It means to get safety net and to be endowed with wish and others. Especially, it is to free from dangers in present and future.

Conclusion

In brief, this Sambuddhe gĒthĒ is a prayer dedicated to the infinity of the attributes of the Buddha, Dhamma and SaŅgha. By developing and reciting that gĒthĒ, one can obtain not only mundane happiness but also the supramundane benefits. The venerable Leidi Sayadawgyi possessed the titles "PiĀkattaya pĒrag| " honoured by the administration board of university, Myanmar and "AggamahĒ-paŌĒita" conferred by the government. He had left over a hundred books. That Sayadaw who was well-versed in scriptures not only recited the Sambuddhe gĒthĒ by self but also founded the association of the Sambuddhe.

As the Sambuddhe gĒthĒ is used to recited and published in various versions, it sheds light on the special study and depth. There are many articles on the benefits of reciting the Sambuddhe gĒthĒs. They freed from the dangers of life, interfere, disaster and defeat. In future, self experienced benefits will be described. The reason is, the three refuges relied on

¹ By Susuka : Sambuddheamyomyo and Tankho Siddhimyah, 124

² MonyinsambuddhecetiyathĒ, 185-188.

are endowed with the quality of “khetta” like mind. So it will be beneficial if the two qualities are accomplished.¹ The third volume of the SañyuttanikĒya depicts thus:

“bhĒvitĒ bahulĕkathĒ abhiĀĀĒya sambodhaya nibbĒnĒya sañvattati.”²

If it is developed repeatedly, it leads to tranquility, higher knowledge, Enlightenment and NibbĒna. If it is developed again and again, one can obtain the happiness being freed from all danger because of the power of 512028 Buddhas, Dhammas and SĒvakas.³

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¹ ©ĕakyaw paĕh-p-70

² S-III-73

³ Myat-Su-Mon-p-25.

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